

Interaction studies in multicomponent liquid mixtures of hexadecane + 1-heptanol with dimethylformamide and tetrahydrofuran

Rita Mehra* and Rekha Israni

Department of Pure and Applied Chemistry, Maharshi Dayanand Saraswati University, Ajmer-305 009, India

E-mail : mehra_rita@rediffmail.com

Manuscript received 2 September 2002, revised 23 July 2003, accepted 1 September 2003

The ultrasonic speed (U), density (ρ) and viscosity (η) of pure hexadecane, 1-heptanol, dimethylformamide (DMF), tetrahydrofuran (THF) and the ternary mixtures of hexadecane + 1-heptanol with DMF and THF have been measured at 25°. From the experimental data, adiabatic compressibility (K_s), and the excess functions which are more sensitive towards molecular interactions viz. excess adiabatic compressibility (K_s^E), excess molar volume (V^E), and excess enthalpy (H^E) have been evaluated. The excess functions are fitted to Redlich Kister relation to estimate the adjustable parameters and their deviations from ideality.

In continuation of our earlier studies¹ on intermolecular interactions in non-aqueous liquid mixtures, we report herein, the results for hexadecane + 1-heptanol with DMF and hexadecane + 1-heptanol with THF at 25°. The determination of ultrasonic speed, density and viscosity and calculation therefrom the adiabatic compressibility and excess parameters in liquid mixtures paves ways to study qualitatively the molecular interactions in liquid mixtures. The components selected for making the ternaries are well known organic liquids and also have wide range of applications in various fields of chemistry besides being used in industries and routine analytical work. Hexadecane is used as a solvent, organic intermediate and ignition standard for diesel fuels. 1-Heptanol is a colourless higher chain fragment alcohol which is used as an organic intermediate, solvent and also in cosmetic formulations. DMF which is a polar solvent is generally used as a solvent for vinyl resins, acid gases, polyacrylic fibres and catalyst in carbonylation reaction as well as in organic synthesis. THF commercially known as cellosolves is a good industrial solvent and figures predominantly in the high energy battery industries and has found applications in the organic synthesis as manifested from physico-chemical studies in the medium.

Results and discussion

The ultrasound speed, density and viscosity data alongwith derived and excess parameters such as K_s , V^E , K_s^E and H^E for hexadecane + 1-heptanol + DMF and hexadecane + 1-heptanol + THF are shown in Table 1. The adiabatic compressibility has been computed using the

Laplace equation ($K_s = U^{-2}\rho^{-1}$). Excess functions Y^E (K_s^E , V^E) have been evaluated as follows :

$$Y^E = Y_{\text{mix}} - (x_1 Y_1 + x_2 Y_2 + x_3 Y_3) \quad (1)$$

$$H^E = x_1 \pi_{i(1)} V_1 + x_2 \pi_{i(2)} V_2 + x_3 \pi_{i(3)} V_3 - \pi_{i(\text{mix})} V_{\text{mix}} \quad (2)$$

All the excess functions are fitted to Redlich Kister relation to estimate the adjustable parameters and their standard deviations from ideality that are listed in Table 2.

Adiabatic compressibility increases when a polar solvent like DMF is added to hexadecane + 1-alkanol system in contrast to addition of a non-polar solvent like THF. The increase in K_s in hexadecane + 1-heptanol + DMF system is consistent with the decrease in sound speed and density because the strong self-association of 1-heptanol molecules is broken due to the addition of the DMF as third component and instead dipole-induced dipole interactions are formed which are relatively weaker in nature. In the system, where THF is the third component, dissociation of alkanol molecules release few dipoles for interaction between unlike molecules than that with DMF as third component. However, due to the non-polar nature of THF, the observed decrease in K_s with mole fraction may be qualitatively interpreted in terms of closer approach of unlike molecules, hence accomodating each other in the interstices leading to reduction in compressibility. The above observation is supported by increase in viscosity of the mixtures which may be ascribed to the fact that at high concentration of THF the possible interstitial accomodation overrides the dissociative effect in alkanols. Further the viscosity of the system is determined mainly by the bulky or less mobile entities of the

Table 1. Ultrasound speed (U), density (ρ), viscosity (η), adiabatic compressibility (K_s), excess adiabatic compressibility (K_s^E), excess molar volume (V^E), and excess enthalpies (H^E) for hexadecane (x_1) + 1-heptanol (x_2) + DMF (x_3) and hexadecane (x_1) + 1-heptanol (x_3) + THF

x_1	x_2	U (m s ⁻¹)	ρ (kg m ⁻³)	$\eta \times 10^3$ (Nm ⁻² s)	K_s (TPa ⁻¹)	$V^E \times 10^{-3}$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	K_s^E (TPa ⁻¹)	H^E (kcal mol ⁻¹)
Hexadecane + 1-heptanol + DMF :								
0.0000	0.3748	1415.6	896.0	2.7336	555.91	-0.0824	-2.68	0.1216
0.0703	0.3571	1398.4	879.1	2.8642	581.27	-0.0763	-7.98	0.1528
0.1574	0.3237	1364.2	863.1	2.8868	622.16	-0.0798	-10.64	0.1729
0.2681	0.2811	1341.5	848.6	2.9047	653.99	-0.0826	-46.13	0.2044
0.3732	0.2408	1318.7	828.7	2.9369	693.81	-0.0867	-19.49	0.2549
0.4576	0.2083	1284.1	801.6	2.9613	755.98	-0.0814	-18.64	0.2049
0.5569	0.1702	1268.3	788.2	2.9946	776.96	-0.0763	-15.49	0.1834
0.6757	0.1245	1248.9	795.4	2.9998	801.85	-0.0718	-10.94	0.1248
0.8203	0.0690	1216.8	790.3	3.0123	854.54	-0.0676	-8.13	0.0917
0.9050	0.0364	1180.6	780.1	3.0248	919.11	-0.0649	-6.49	0.0749
1.0000	0.0000	1181.0	773.3	3.0320	727.15	-	-	-
Hexadecane + 1-heptanol + THF :								
0.0000	0.3695	1279.1	513.4	1.6789	1190.12	-0.0813	-2.18	0.1428
0.0672	0.3417	1251.4	522.6	1.7084	1120.86	-0.0896	-3.94	0.1594
0.1576	0.3118	1248.3	561.9	1.8294	1140.74	-0.0896	-6.18	0.1763
0.2595	0.2721	1241.6	609.8	1.9626	1059.31	-0.0804	-12.49	0.1926
0.3629	0.2341	1231.9	641.7	2.1498	1025.40	-0.0757	-18.98	0.2184
0.4941	0.1859	1228.3	672.3	2.3166	984.62	-0.0748	-23.46	0.1817
0.6030	0.1459	1214.8	701.5	2.5284	965.07	-0.0709	-20.11	0.1623
0.7023	0.0977	1198.7	742.2	2.7244	937.68	-0.0659	-16.48	0.1413
0.8137	0.0684	1190.4	753.1	2.8988	937.04	-0.0601	-10.21	0.1298
0.9011	0.0361	1186.5	762.4	2.9846	931.71	-0.0583	-8.64	0.1034
1.0000	0.0000	1181.0	773.3	3.0320	927.15	-	-	-

system which causes the variation in strength of interactions. Table 1 indicates that values of K_s for ternary systems decreases monotonically in hexadecane + 1-heptanol + DMF and hexadecane + 1-heptanol + THF. The observation of K_s in such solvent mixtures suggests the absence of complex formation in the ternary mixtures as also reported by other workers^{2,3}.

Treszczanowicz *et al.* explained the behaviour of V^E for

Table 2. Value of adjustable parameters and their standard deviation

	a_0	a_1	a_2	σ
Hexadecane + 1-heptanol + DMF :				
K_s^E (Tpa ⁻¹)	-6.09	7.08	8.13	1.4
$V^E \times 10^{-3}$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	-0.24	2.18	6.13	2.1
H^E (kcal mol ⁻¹)	-36.18	21.98	3.24	0.82
Hexadecane + 1-heptanol + THF :				
K_s^E (Tpa ⁻¹)	-3.48	7.08	10.49	2.01
$V^E \times 10^{-3}$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	-0.2	2.48	2.49	1.44
H^E (kcal mol ⁻¹)	24.66	78.46	3.18	0.16

alcohol + n-alkane in terms of a net effect resulting from several opposite effects – chemical, physical and structural. The chemical contribution from partial destruction of H-bonded structure of alkanols, physical contribution from the fact that dispersion interactions between unlike components are weaker than those between like molecules leading to expansion upon mixing and the structural contribution arises from interstitial accommodation of n-alkane molecules within the H-bonded structure of l-alkanol changing free volume thereof. The result of this work indicates slight dominance of structural effect. Mixing of DMF with 1-heptanol tends to break the associates present in alcohol molecules with initial increase in K_s^E and V^E . However, due to hydrogen bonding between DMF and 1-heptanol molecules, in addition to the interstitial accommodation of the component molecules, there is a compensating effect resulting in an overall decrease in V^E and K_s^E with increase in mole fraction of hexadecane for the ternary systems under study. In view of the strong proton accepting ability of DMF, due to its higher polar carbonyl bond with high percentage of ionic charac-

ter, negative K_S^E and V^E may be regarded as an evidence for the formation of a hydrogen bond between the carbonyl oxygen of DMF and the hydrogen atom of the hydroxyl group of 1-heptanol molecules. The small negative V^E and K_S^E values for the two ternaries under study over the whole range of composition suggest that interstitial accommodation and hydrogen bonding slightly dominates over the disruption of hydrogen bonds in self associated 1-heptanol molecules. However, the steric hinderance of the two methyl groups of DMF decrease its ability to form H-bond. On the other hand, THF is a non-polar solvent which in addition to corresponding binary system of hexadecane + 1-heptanol will not be able to release so much dipoles as much DMF can, so the bonded interactions between the component molecules in this case will be less as compared to hexadecane + 1-heptanol + DMF³⁻⁶.

The positive values of H^E are consistent to the endothermic effect due to the breaking of the dipole interactions of alkanol molecules on being mixed with DMF and/or THF in the two systems under study. The small endothermic effect in the ternary system with DMF as third component as compared to THF may be attributed to random orientation of DMF molecules in pure state in contrast to the latter. These results are in agreement with those of V^E and K_S^E as explained above because they indicate the break down of association of the polar molecules and hence exhibit measure interactions. Thus we can make a reasonable consideration that positive values of H^E which are reported to be due to dispersive forces by other workers hereby also suggest interactions of less strength^{7,8}.

Thus, we conclude that the strength of interactions over the entire composition range decreases in the two ternaries under investigation. However, the variation of K_S and the small difference in the values of excess parameters of the two ternaries can be accounted to the nature of the third component (polar/non polar) added to the binary system of hexadecane + 1-heptanol.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade with a purity >99%. The purity of the components was ascertained

Table 3. Parameters of pure components

	Refractive indices		$\rho/\text{kg m}^{-3}$		Boiling point/ $^{\circ}\text{C}$	
	Obs.	Lit.	Obs.	Lit.	Obs.	Lit.
Hexadecane	1.4341	1.4345 ^a	772.9	773.1 ^a	287.0	286.8
1-Heptanol	1.4213	1.4214 ^b	822.1	822.0 ^a	175.3	175.8
Dimethylformamide	1.4286	1.4290 ^b	944.4	944.5 ^b	133.1	133.0
Tetrahydrofuran	1.4071	1.4072 ^a	889.0	889.2 ^a	66.1	66.0

^aAt 20 $^{\circ}$, ^bat 25 $^{\circ}$.

by comparing densities, boiling points and refractive indices of pure components with those reported in literature⁹ and are reported in Table 3. The sound speeds of pure liquids and their mixtures were measured using a single crystal interferometer operating at 2 MHz frequency with uncertainty of $\pm 0.03\%$ in measurements. The densities were measured by using a bicapillary pycnometer which are accurate upto $\pm 0.024\%$. The viscosities of pure liquids and their ternaries were measured by using a Ostwald's viscometer with a percentage error of $\pm 0.09\%$. The temperature of the test liquids and their ternaries was maintained to an accuracy of $\pm 0.1^{\circ}$.

References

1. R. Mehra and R. Israni, *Proc. Intl. Conf. Exhibit. Ultrason.*, 1999, **1**, 234; *Indian J. Pure Appl. Phys.*, 2000, **28**, 81; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **79**, 145.
2. R. K. Dewan, J. Kaur and S. K. Mehta, *Acous. Letts.*, 1985, **9**, 13.
3. R. Mehra and R. Israni, *J. Pure Appl. Ultrason.*, 2001, **23**, 63; *Indian J. Chem. Tech.*, 2002, **9**, 341.
4. A. Ali and A. K. Nain, *Phys. Chem. Liq.*, 1999, **37**, 161.
5. J. D. Pandey, N. Dubey, D. K. Dwivedi and K. Dey, *Phys. Chem. Liq.*, 2001, **39**, 781.
6. A. Pal, W. Singh and H. K. Sharma *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1998, **37**, 507.
7. A. J. Treszczanowicz, O. Kiyohara and G. C. Benson, *J. Chem. Thermodyn.*, 1981, **13**, 875.
8. R. Bravo, M. Pintos, M. C. Baluja and M. I. Paz Andrade, *J. Chem. Thermodyn.*, 1984, **16**, 73.
9. J. A. Dean, "Lange's Handbook of Chemistry", McGraw Hill Book Co., 13th. ed., 1972.